

Empirical Relationship of Big Five Personality Traits and Affective Commitment Among the Public Sector Employees.

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Abstract:

The study explores the relationship of the Big-Five personality traits with affective commitment among the public sector employees. Personality is an important antecedent of employee commitment with the organization. Self-administered questionnaire assessing personality traits and affective commitment was collected from 150 managerial level of employee and academic level of the public sector employees. The collected data were analyzed using descriptive analysis and correlation analysis. The results of the study indicated that extraversion, conscientiousness and agreeableness traits were significantly correlated with affective commitment. Results on neuroticism and openness to experience traits did not show significant relationship. The findings of the study add to the body of knowledge in the refinement of organizational commitment models from dispositional perspective

Keywords: *Big Five Personality Traits; Affective Commitment; Organizational Commitment; Public Employees*

INTRODUCTION

Organizations play a significant part in the economic progress of a state. Among all the assets of an organization, critical success factor is composed of its competent human resource. To achieve the objective of having competent manpower one of the essential parts of HRM, agreeing with Crowley (1999) and Johnson (2000), is to hire a right type of person with the right kind of personality who becomes committed to the organization. Personality appears to be a vital determining factor of employee performance in the organization. According to Scholl, there is something in individual personality or disposition that leads to exhibiting the committed behavior. Simply speaking, there are employees in an organization who want to remain in the organization. According to Meyer and Allen (1996) committed individuals have more chances to keep their jobs in the organization; they show a higher level of employee engagement (Tanriverdi, 2008), job satisfaction and work motivation (Tella, Ayeni, & Popoola, 2007). Employees with lower level of commitment are linked with low levels of individual performance, lesser engagement with the work (DeCotiis & Summers, 1987) and inclined to leave the organization. Non-committed employee describes the organization in negative terms to other employees in the market which works to impede the organization's ability to attract and hire high quality human capital. In contrast, a high level of commitment among the workforce is more likely to produce social capital that help in creating, retaining, and transferring knowledge within an organization (Park & Rainey, 2007) and attract other employees in the market to be a part of that organization.

Organizational commitment is considered a significant indicator of job attitude not only in the field of management and organizational behavior, but in human resource management as well because it predicts the turnover rate better than job satisfaction. Commitment as an individual attitude and behavior has been linked to other positive organizational behaviors like organizational citizenship behavior (Williams & Anderson, 1991), absenteeism and job involvement (Wegge, Schmidt, Parkes, & Dick, 2007) and turnover intentions (Jaros, 1997). In the management literature, organizational commitment has quite a long history (Becker, 1960). The idea of organizational commitment in the research can be mapped out through many aspects which include economic, social, psychological and behavioral perspective and the reality is that quite a lot of earlier authors described commitment in various manners which consist of several foundations, as dubbed by manifold indicators. Highly dedicated and committed human capital is not only a valued asset for the organization, but a competitive edge as well, which can be barely copied by the competitors in the market.

Although researchers identified various antecedents, that are contributing towards organizational commitment. Significant attention has been given to environmental and structural factor while completely ignoring the dispositional factor that also play an important part in determining the organizational commitment among employees. Therefore the proposed research, aims to discover the relationship between personality traits and affective commitment and attempt to fill the gain the literature pertaining to antecedent of organizational commitment.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Big Five Personality Traits

In the field of organizational behavior, Big Five model of personality is one of the most salient archetypal to test the personality of the employees (Goldberg, 1990; John & Srivastava, 1999). The five factor model is used to describe employee's independent personality types that constitute five comprehensive personality traits consisting Agreeableness, Extraversion, Conscientiousness, Openness to Experience and Neuroticism. These five broad types of personality provide a useful taxonomy to test the individual differences among employee. Extraversion includes traits such as sociable, outgoing, aggressive and full of energy (Barrick & Mount, 1991). The second trait of personality which is mainly based on the individual's interpersonal relationship is called

Agreeableness. Agreeableness comprise traits such as flexibility, soft hearted, cooperative, trusting, good natured and forgiving (Barrick & Mount, 1991). Conscientiousness is the trait that reflects thorough, hardworking, careful, organized, responsible and persevering people (Barrick & Mount, 1991) and is linked with important work attitudes like job performance (Hurtz & Donovan, 2000). Neuroticism includes traits like anxiousness, depression, anger, worry, and insecurity (Barrick & Mount, 1991). These people may not want to remain in the organization because they usually put themselves in situations where they foster the negative attitude towards their coworkers. Openness to experience is the trait that pertains to being intelligent, imaginative, curious, cultured, original, artistically sensitive and broad minded people (Barrick & Mount, 1991) and is related with work outcomes like employee engagement and organizational productivity (Srivastava, Chandra, & Shirish, 2015).

2.2 Organizational Commitment

Commitment of the employees with their organization plays a vital role in achieving organizational effectiveness and efficiency by fostering the productivity and accountability for accomplishing organizational objectives. According to Meyer and Allen (1996), organizational commitment is usually defined as a “psychological link between the employee and his or her organization that makes it less likely that the employee will voluntarily leave the organization” (p. 42). It is characterized by three factors recognized by Steer, Mowday and Porter (1987) and stated as “(a) a belief of the employees in and acceptance of goals and values, (b) a willingness of employee to exert effort on the behalf of the organization, and (c) a strong desire to maintain membership in that organization” (p. 29). While researchers and theorists have been defining organizational commitment in many diverse manners in the last three decades, they all recognize that it is an intricate and multidimensional concept of job attitude (Meyer & Allen, 1996). The concept of organizational commitment has been defined on the bases of three dimensions of commitment. The first one is known as ‘Affective Commitment’ that reflects an emotional bond consisting of employees’ identification and attachment with the organization’s goals. The second dimension is known as ‘Continuance Commitment’ which is identified as the perceived economic and social costs related with quitting the organization. ‘Normative Commitment’, the third dimension, asserts that employees remain committed with the organization because of moral reasons or moral obligation. At this commitment level, individuals feel obligated to continue within the organization either because of the trustworthiness or a duty to reciprocate. In opposition to that, affectively committed employees remain in the same place because they “want to” stay in the organization, whereas other employees stay with the firm because of the sense of moral responsibility or to protect oneself against costs associated with leaving.

2.3 Big Five personality traits and Affective Commitment

In the present study, we proposed that Big five personality traits are strongly associated with affective commitment of the public employees as it is the most desirable dimension of organizational commitment in which employees remain in the organization because they ‘want to’, and thus more likely to display the positive behavior such as organizational citizenship behavior, job satisfaction and lesser rate of turnover intentions. From the literature, it can be observed that continuance commitment is mostly focused on the extrinsic benefits, whereas many studies found a high correlation between affective and normative commitment which doubts this construct as an individual dimension (Meyer & Allen; 1990, Prince Muller; 1997). Moreover, Tayyeb and Riaz (2004) have mentioned that by cultivating any one aspect of the model of commitment we can affect the other two dimensions of commitment as well because they are associated with each other. In the view of the above, present model will focus on examining the relationship of all the five traits of Big Five model with Affective commitment in Pakistani context with the view to exhibit cross cultural differences, if any, and better understanding of the H.R management in public organizations.

Extraversion:

Extraversion is the interpersonal personality trait of Big-Five model. People who are characterized as an extrovert, love to enjoy interacting with others and are generally viewed as full of energy. They tend to be enthusiastic and usually action oriented people (Barrick & Mount, 1991). In short, Barrick and Mount (1991) summarized extroverts are individuals who exhibit energy, assertiveness, talkativeness, sociability and positive emotionality. Erdheim, Wang and Zickar, (2006) and Watson and Clark (1997) identified, in positive and negative affectivity research, that positive emotionality is the central part of extraversion. Thus affective commitment which normally regarded as employees’ positive reactions towards their organization may be associated more with individual who are high in extraversion and assert themselves in positive emotions (Cropanzano, James, & Konovsky, 1993; Barsky et al., 2003; Williams, Gavin, & Williams, 1996). Based on that we can rationally presume that individuals who are high on extraversion may have higher level of affective commitment than those who are introverted. Empirical findings also depict a relationship between extraversion and affective commitment in western societies (Erdheim et al., 2006; Gelade, Dobson, & Gilbert, 2006; Williams et al., 1996). For instance, Erdheim et al., (2006) discovered a positive association between extraversion and affective commitment. Hence on the basis of the above evidence in the literature, it can be hypothesized that

H1= Extraversion will be positively related to Affective organizational Commitment of employees

Agreeableness:

Agreeableness is another Big-Five personality trait which is primarily centered on the individual’s interpersonal relationship. Organ and Lingl (1995) claimed that people who are characterized as agreeable value getting along with others These people are ready to compensate their interest over others employees’ interest (Barrick & Mount, 1991). They tend to focus on the quality of relationship with others on the principle of trust and mutual help (DeNeve & Cooper, 1998; Judge, et al., 1999). Barrick & Mount

(1991) agreeable people are mostly kind, generous, unselfish, cooperative and trustworthy. Individuals high on agreeableness have a tendency to be flexible and forgiving while dealing with other employees because they are motivated to fulfill their fundamental need of affiliation (Barrick et al., 2002) and emotional warmth. In other words, this emotional warmth and affiliation encourage employee's social identity with his/her work environment and promote a sense of belonging and identification with organizational values and goals. Consequently, this emotional bond creates a pleasant work environment and reinforces the emotional attachment with the organization (Ilies, Fulmer, Spitzmuller, & Johnson, 2009). Empirical findings of previous research have also supported a bond between agreeableness and affective commitment in a western context. Therefore, it is reasonable to presume that people high on agreeableness are more likely to have a positive relationship with affective commitment. For an instance Holton and Naquin (2002) and Morrison (1997) revealed that affective commitment is strongly related to agreeableness. Based on the above argument, we hypothesize that

H2= Agreeableness will be positively related to Affective organizational Commitment of the employees

Conscientiousness:

Conscientiousness is a trait of personality that has strong dispositional roots with job attitudes such as organization commitment, job satisfaction and job involvement (Hochwarter, Perrewé, Ferris, & Guericco, 1999). Conscientious people are characterized as self-disciplined, perseverant and achievement-oriented. They aim for achievement and prefer to make plans and follow through them (Barrick & Mount, 1991). Researcher defined conscientiousness as "a generalized work involvement tendency (i.e., a liking for rule-governed behavior that probably is more characteristic of work in organizations than in other life domains)" (Organ and Lingl 1995, p. 341). A positive correlation has been evident in the literature between conscientiousness and job involvement (Organ & Lingl, 1995). Meyer theory also identified that people who are highly affectively committed with their organization exhibit high involvement and show commitment to its goals. It is therefore presumed that conscientiousness, by enhancing the level of employee's involvement in their organization and engagement with their job, would allow them to be more affectively committed with their organization. Empirical evidence also supports a positive correlation between conscientiousness and affective commitment in the western context (Erdheim, Wang & Zickar, 2006; Matzler & Renzl, 2007; Naquin & Holton, 2002). Hence it is hypothesized that

H3= Conscientiousness will be positively related with Affective organizational Commitment of the employees

Openness to experience:

Bozionelos (2004) defined openness to experience as "receptivity of new ideas, inventiveness, multiplicity of interests, flexibility of thought and the tendency to develop idealistic ideas and goals" (p. 71). Open individuals are characterized as having intellectual curiosity, creativity and innovation. Openness is also described as the extent to which a person is imaginative, cultured, curious, comes up with original ideas and artistically sensitive (Barrick & Mount, 1991). DeNeve and Cooper (1998) described that "openness is a double-edged sword that predisposes an individual to feel both the good and the bad more deeply, leaving its directional influence on affective reactions" (p. 199). People who are high on this trait of Big-Five are likely to expend their time and effort to complete projects on time and are believed to be more productive (Lounsbury, Sundstrom, Loveland, & Gibson, 2003). When the work environment will allow these employees to use their imaginative and creative skills on the job and appreciate their divergent thinking, it will in turn aid in developing an affective commitment towards their company. Therefore, it can be assumed in the above argument that there is a connection between openness to experience and employees' affective commitment. While research on this is very limited, and there is no conclusive evidence that individuals high on openness to experience are affectively committed with their firm, according to the western setting (Erdheim et al., 2006). Thus, it can be postulated that

H4= Openness to experience will be positively related with Affective organizational Commitment of the employees.

Neuroticism

Neuroticism is among the prominent traits investigated by various studies of personality (Costa & McCrae, 1988b; Judge, et al., 1999). Neurotic people, mostly tend to experience negative emotions easily which include nervousness, anxiety, depression, and excessive worry (Bozionelos, 2004). As this trait of personality is negative in nature, Bozionelos (2004) sustains that "neurotic individuals should be more likely to develop negative attitudes and behaviors towards their work" (p. 70). Employees who are high on neuroticism, choose to put themselves in situations where they foster the negative effect. This attitude of individuals in return decreases the likelihood of employees to build a positive emotional bond with their organization. It is therefore reasonable to assume that there will be a negative relationship between neuroticism and the level of affective commitment. Empirical evidence also illustrates a significant negative association concerning Neuroticism and Affective commitment in American circumstance (Gelade et al., 2006; Naquin & Holton, 2002). Gelade et al (2006) also exhibited that the level of affective commitment was higher in nations where neuroticism was lower. In the light of the above research, we can hypothesize that

H5= Neuroticism will be negatively related with Affective organizational Commitment of the employees

3. METHODOLOGY

A cross sectional research study has been conducted on the employees of a public sector university to determine the relationship between their personality characteristics and their level of Affective commitment with their organization. Survey method is considered the most appropriate method for analyzing attitudes and beliefs of respondent (Bryman, 2012). The data were gathered through self-administered questionnaire as the respondent of this study were well educated to understand and fill-in the questionnaire and provide information needed for a reasonable level of generalization of the findings to other public sector universities.

3.1 Sample and Procedures

The sample of the study consisted of 150 employees from across 17 out of 72 institutions of the University of the Punjab. The sample included both the faculty members of the university (54.7 %; Table-I at Appendix-C) and the managerial employees, BPS scale 17 and above (45.3 %; Table-I at Appendix-C). 68% of the employees held the permanent faculty and managerial position in the university while 32 % were working on the contractual basis (Table-II at Appendix-D). Among those, 62.7% were males and 37.3 % were females (Table-III at Appendix-E). 30% of the respondent were single, 70% were married (Table-VI at Appendix-F). In terms of the qualification, 12.70 % had got education till bachelors level, 32 % till masters level, 35.3 % (highest percentage) were qualified till MPhil level and 20 % were qualified to PhD level (table-V at Appendix-G). The majority of the respondents were in the age group of 20-40 years (78.70 %) and the remaining 21.30 % were above 41 years old (Table-IV at Appendix-H). Data collection was completed in about one month after exhaustive following up and pursuance as the masses were generally hesitant to spare time for this process. The questionnaire had been left with them and picked up in person to save time. 200 questionnaires were distributed among employees out of whom 150 were returned giving a response rate of 75%. The participants were ensured the confidentiality and anonymity of their responses. The letter of consent was designed and signed from the respondent before data collection. The data collection was completed in a very cordial and pleasant atmosphere. The respondents were assured the privacy of information provided by them.

3.2 Measures

For all items, a 5 point Likert scale had been used which consist one as “strongly disagree” and 5 as “strongly agree”.

3.2.1 Big Five Personality Traits

Big five personality was measured with 44 items adapted from the Big Five Personality inventory developed by Oliver P John (2008). These 44 items measure employee personality type on its Five characteristics. First dimension extraversion consist of eight item measure and sample items was “I am talkative”, second dimension of Big Five was agreeableness scale comprised of nine items sample item like “Is helpful and unselfish with others”. Likewise, third dimension consists of conscientiousness which also included nine item measure e-g “does a thorough job”and neuroticism consist of eight items measure, for instance “Is depressed and blue”. The last dimension of personality traits was openness to experience which included ten items and sample item was: “ Is mostly comes up with new ideas”

3.2.2 Affective Commitment Scale

Questionnaire developed by Meyer and Allen (1991) was used for measuring affective commitment of employees, which consist of seven items measure and example of items was “I will be very happy to spend the rest of my career in this organization ”

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The initial analyses of the data were done through descriptive statistics and correlation to describe and explore the relationship between Big-Five personality traits and affective commitment. Perception of personality traits reported by the employees (frequencies of the independent variable), (Table-1) showed a considerable number of people representing a medium level of perception in personality traits. Such a medium level of perception of personality traits may be evident due to the social desirability among the respondents belonging to collectivist culture of Pakistan, where people have strong desirability of maintaining a good relationship and required social acceptance in the society, they are more likely to be deceptive for the sake of public image management (Triandis & Suh, 2002). The concentration of the people on medium level of perception of personality traits may also be a reflection of self-report bias where people have a strong tendency to paint them in a favorable image instead of giving the honest answers.

TABLE-1 PERCEPTION OF BIG-FIVE PERSONALITY TRAITS

Personality perception	Frequency	Percentage
Positive	37	24.6
Moderate	97	64.6
Poor	16	10.6
Total	150	100

Table – 2 shows that the employee showing high level of Affective commitment aggregate at 32.6%, however 10.67% fall in a low level of commitment. Similarly like personality traits, the level of affective commitment among the respondents depicts times a large number of individuals falling under the medium category of commitment (56.67%).

TABLE-2: AFFECTIVE COMMITMENT WITH THE ORGANIZATION

Level of commitment	Frequency	Percent
High	49	32.6
Medium	85	56.67
Low	16	10.67
Total	150	100

TABLE-3: CORRELATIONS BETWEEN BIG FIVE PERSONALITY TRAITS AND AFFECTIVE COMMITMENT

	Affective commitment	Big-Five Personality	Extraversion	Agreeableness	Conscientiousness	Neuroticism	Openness to experience
Affective commitment	1.00						
Big-Five Personality	.241**	1.00					
Extraversion	.218**	.603**	1.00				
Agreeableness	.254**	.609**	.168*	1.00			
Conscientiousness	.182*	.524**	.365**	.402**	1.00		
Neuroticism	-.152	.027	-.368**	-.170*	-.514**	1.00	
Openness to experience	.140	.693**	.333**	.271**	.154	-.088	1.00

N = 150

* Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed)

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)

The analysis of the correlations between the Big-Five personality traits shows that overall a relatively weak correlation exists among the level of affective commitment ($r = .241$; $p < .01$), and the personality of employee which is consistent with previous research linking personality traits with dimension of affective commitment (Erdheim et al., 2006, Naquin and Holton; 2002,). The weak relationship between personality traits and affective commitment signifies that the personality is not the only factor that is responsible for developing affective commitment. Many previous studies suggest that the organizational structure, labor market conditions and job related factors also play an important role toward building the commitment level (Iverson & Buttigieg; 1999). However, significant relationship of personality traits relationship with affective commitment in present study empirically supports Meyer and Allen (1997) proposition that persons with specific personality traits are more or less likely to become attached to their organization. It is empirically evident that the personality factors contributing in developing an affective commitment level among employees in the context of this study.

Results of correlation analysis (Table-3) support our first hypothesis that there exists a significant positive relationship between Extraversion trait of personality and Affective commitment ($r = .218$; $p < .01$) which is also in line with the previous studies conducted in western contexts (Erdheim et al., 2006; Gelade et al., 2006; Williams et al., 1996). This shows that extroverts people

who are characterized as sociable and who love to interact with others have a tendency to be affectively committed with their company and that they want to stay and maintain membership in the organization. This may also be due to the fact that extrovert people are sociable in nature and make friends easily in the organization and they don't want to leave the organization, because of their social circle .

Further analysis of correlations supports our second hypothesis that relationship exists between personality trait of Agreeableness and affective commitment. In fact, Agreeableness and affective commitment have the strongest positive correlation (0.254; $p < 0.01$) among all the personality traits listed in table – 3. This finding is also consistent with the previous research and the reason may be that agreeableness is an interpersonal trait of personality, in which relationship between the people is based on mutual cooperation and trust (DeNeve & Cooper, 1998; Judge, et al., 1999). Employee scoring high on this trait showed that they can easily get along with others in a satisfying and pleasant way. (Organ & Lingl, 1995,) because they are motivated to fulfill the need of affiliation (Barrick & Mount, 1991) and emotional warmth; which in return instigates employees to identify with the environment and promote a sense of belonging and identification with organization goals and values. (Erdheim et al. 2006). Again the possible reason of this strong relationship with affective commitment might be because of the culture of the education sector where social interaction is highly required because of daily interaction and communication among students and universities employee for day to day activity.

Results on the Conscientiousness trait of Big-Five personality model showed a positive relationship with affective commitment ($r = 0.182$; $p < 0.05$), and supported our third hypothesis, but the relationship was quite weak as compared to Agreeableness and Extroversion. An employee who scores high on this trait is hard working and achievement oriented people and have a great tendency to be highly involved in their work. Since high involvement in the work and desire to achieve are not recognized/acknowledged in the public sector because of less developed performance management practices in Pakistan, the conscientious employee does not appear to be attached with their organization to a great extent.

The relationship between Openness to Experience and Affective commitment ($r = 0.152$; $p < 0.05$) is quite weak but still positive. Individuals who score high on the trait are creative and have divergent thinking and therefore may be more prone to working for more innovative hence lesser committed to their organization. This result of an association among Openness to Experience and Affective commitment is consistent with prior studies by Bergman (2004) and Erdheim et al. (2006) signifying a lack of conclusive evidence.

Similarly the relationship between Neuroticism and affective commitment does not appear to be significant ($r = -0.152$; $p < 0.01$). Neuroticism is considered to be the main source of negative emotions, for which a negative association between negative emotions and organizational commitment in the previous studies (Cropanzano et al., 1993; Thoresen et al., 2003) was observed (Kumar & Bakhshi, 2010). Insignificant results in this study may be due to the fact that people do not want to reveal or show their negative emotions like anger, anxiety and depression in our culture because of high drive of social acceptance in the society.

5-CONCLUSION

The study was aimed to find the relationship of Big-Five personality traits with Affective organizational commitment amongst the public sector employees. Data was collected from the faculty and administrative/management employees of the Punjab University who were on BPS 17 and above scale. Correlation analysis of the collected data revealed a positive linkage between the employee's personality traits and organizational commitment which is in accord with the previous findings. Though the contemporary research shows that people who are high on Extraversion, Agreeableness, Conscientiousness and Openness to Experience, and low on Neuroticism, should also score high on Affective commitment, the results of this study revealed a significant positive relationship of Extraversion and Agreeableness with Affective commitment. Whereas a relationship between Openness to Experience and Neuroticism was not found significant. From the present study data analysis and discussion, it can be concluded that Big-Five personality traits play a significant part in developing the organizational commitment of an individual employee. As it is a pioneer study on public sector in Pakistan of investigating the relationship between dispositional factors and Affective commitment with the organization, it is expected to motivate and pave a way for the future researchers to carry out more studies on the subject in the context of Pakistan. It may also provide researchers and practitioners to form a cross cultural comparison for integration and refinement towards global management. The association between overall personalities of the employees and Affective commitment was not quite strong supporting the view of various researchers that job related factors, organizational factors and cultural differences of the country also play important role in developing a strong bond with the organization. Jang (2012) identified that personality types differ from context to context and from one culture to another, depending upon the personality types prevalent in the culture. However, the present research has empirically proved that the personality factors do contribute towards creating Affective Organizational Commitment.

6 PRACTICAL IMPLICATIONS

The present study has provided an empirical evidence that personality traits contribute towards development of commitment towards an organization. Committed individuals have more chances to keep their jobs in the organization and will show a higher level of employee engagement (Tanriverdi, 2008), job satisfaction and work motivation (Tella, Ayeni, & Popoola, 2007). The findings of this study will help the policy makers and HR managers to devise a selection process that consists of employee's psychological testing to determine the desirable personality dimensions and to induce highly affectively committed workforce. As

those employees who are predisposed to be emotionally attached and committed to their organization are more satisfied with their work and show better performance. This study might help in retaining valuable employees in the organization, in turn, will result in ultimately improving the organizational performance, increasing the revenue and reducing the turnover rate of the organization.

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